

HYMORITIS - SYMPTOMS, TREATMENT, METHODS OF FOLK MEDICINE, PREVENTION

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Abstract. *Snusitis is a disease characterized by inflammation of the mucous membrane of the nasal sinus (upper jaw cavity), it is considered a type of sinusitis and is the most common ENT disease. Depending on the severity of the disease, it can be acute or chronic. If the disease is diagnosed early and has not progressed to serious forms, in most cases the method of treating sinusitis at home is also effective.*

Keywords: *Causes of sinusitis, Symptoms and signs of sinusitis, Classification, Complications, Treatment of sinusitis, Treatment of sinusitis using folk medicine, Prevention of sinusitis.*

WHAT IS A DISEASE?

Hymoritis - treatment, prevention, disease symptoms, prevention

The location of the sinuses

The sinuses of the upper jaw or the side of the nose are air cavities, whose task is to equalize atmospheric and intracranial pressure, perform resonator functions, and purify and moisten the air. The passages of the side cavities of the nose go out into the nasal cavity, and inside it is covered with a mucous membrane attached to the bone. Inflammation of that mucous membrane is called sinusitis.

CAUSES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYMORITIS

Most often, the main cause of sinusitis is an upper respiratory tract infection or allergy, so the development of this disease increases in the autumn-winter season.

In addition, failure to treat certain diseases, harmful external factors can also cause sinusitis, including:

- Caries of upper jaw teeth;
- Weakening of the immune system;
- Injuries of the mucous membrane surrounding the sinuses of the nose;
- Staying in a room with excessively dry or windy air for a long time;
- Non-observance of oral hygiene;
- Fungal diseases of the mucous membrane;
- Bacteria (staphylococci);
- Tuberculosis;
- Work in harmful production;
- Anomalies of nasopharyngeal development and its injuries;
- Presence of tumors;
- Frequent use of nasal drops;
- Allergic reactions with rhinitis;
- Deformation (bent) of the nasal septum and, as a result, violation of air circulation in the sinuses;

- Chronic infections — pharyngitis, tonsillitis, etc.

SYMPTOMS AND SIGNS OF HAYMORITIS

The initial symptoms of sinusitis are body temperature rise, fever, weakness, runny nose, and pain in the face. The pain spreads to the forehead, teeth and temple. In addition, redness and swelling of the eyelids may be noted. When children have sinusitis, their moodiness and fatigue are also noticeable. At the same time, depending on how the sinusitis develops, the symptoms of the disease can also differ.

Acute sinusitis develops against the background of ARVI symptoms and is expressed by the following symptoms:

- Fever;
- Pain in the joints;
- Pain in the upper jaw and nose;
- Strong flu;
- Headache, eye pain.

And chronic sinusitis develops gradually, its symptoms are:

- Chronic rhinitis;
- Pain in the eye area;
- Conjunctivitis;
- Often headaches.

CLASSIFICATION

Sinusitis is a disease with many types. Today, doctors distinguish the following types of the disease:

Catarrhal sinusitis. The disease is characterized by inflammation of the mucous membrane, swelling and redness of the nasal cavity. Catarrhal sinusitis is more common among children. The causes are viral infection, allergic flu and injuries of the nasal mucosa. Characteristic symptoms include loss of appetite, fever and signs of general intoxication.

Bilateral sinusitis. It is more common in complications of inflammation of maxillary sinuses. Its prominent symptoms include swelling, excessive discharge from the nose, runny nose, increased body temperature, general intoxication, as well as watery eyes and apathetic states. The development of this type of disease can be caused by infectious and inflammatory processes.

When suspecting bilateral sinusitis, the otolaryngologist prescribes complex treatment - drugs and physiotherapy procedures.

Polyposis sinusitis. This type of disease cannot be treated with drugs. As a rule, the development of polyposis sinusitis is associated with allergies, disorders of the anatomical structure of the nasal components, and inflammation. The main symptoms are frequent discharge in the form of mouth breathing and mucus from the nose. In addition, there is a violation of the ability to taste and a decrease in appetite. Treatment is performed by a surgeon. If the size of the polyps is small, drug treatment methods can also be used, but the result is not always noticeable.

Allergic sinusitis. The reason for this is the influence of the nasal sinuses. Its symptoms are tearing, swelling, fever, headaches and general weakness. The disease is observed mainly in autumn and spring. To treat allergic sinusitis, it is necessary to first identify the allergen and limit the patient's contact with it. As a result of a complete examination, the attending physician prescribes anti-allergen therapy, and then general supportive drugs.

Purulent sinusitis. It is often a consequence of untreated or missed infectious diseases of the upper respiratory tract. The causes of this type of sinusitis are pathogenic microorganisms and products of their vital activity. If the purulent type of the disease is not paid enough attention and its treatment is delayed, it can spread to the bones and nearby tissues and organs.

Odontogenic sinusitis. It develops as a result of the pathogen moving from the infected upper jaw teeth and oral cavity to the side cavities of the nose. The causative agents are Escherichia coli, staphylococci, streptococci and their combinations. Perforative and nonperforative forms of odontogenic sinusitis are also distinguished. The first is observed when a fissure is formed between the oral cavity and the sinuses of the upper jaw as a result of the extraction of the upper jaw tooth. It is through this fissure that pathogens reach the sinuses.

In addition, sinusitis can be infectious, vasomotor, exudative, productive, necrotic and atrophic.

Infectious sinusitis can be viral, bacterial or fungal in nature.

Vasomotor inflammation of the side of the nose is associated with blood vessel dysfunction.

The exudative type refers to the presence of pus in the sinuses.

In productive sinusitis, various tumors are formed in the sinus itself, for example, polypous tumors.

If necrosis is noted in the sinuses, then the necrotic type of the disease is said.

Atrophic sinusitis is diagnosed when the nutrition of the tissues of the sinus and nasal cavity is disturbed.

COMPLICATIONS

If there are delays in the treatment of sinusitis, this disease can lead to serious diseases such as meningitis and encephalitis, inflammatory diseases of the eyes and ears.

If the disease continues to develop, the patient may face problems related to the kidneys, heart, eyes, joints, and even the brain.

It is very easy to diagnose acute sinusitis using radiography. In determining the chronic form, doctor's qualification, computer tomography will help. If an accurate diagnosis is made, other diseases can be excluded.

TREATMENT OF HAYMORITIS

At the moment, there are many methods of treatment of goitritis, but how effective it is is questionable. And the question that many people are interested in, is it possible to treat sinusitis without puncture?

CURRENT MEDICINE METHODS

If sinusitis is manifested in an acute form as a complication of ARVI, the doctor may recommend using nasal drops, taking mucolytic drugs and rinsing the sinuses with saline water. Antibiotics and antihistamines are often prescribed. But excessive use of nasal drops can cause harm instead of benefit, because they dry out the nasal mucosa and create the basis for further exacerbation of the disease.

Antibiotics can be administered locally by rinsing the sinuses, as well as prescribed in the form of tablets or injections. Which type of antibiotic is used is chosen only by the doctor.

PUNCTURE METHOD

In this case, an antiseptic solution is injected into the sinus under pressure, and purulent exudate is washed out. This method is carried out under the supervision of a doctor. But because the process is painful and unpleasant, it is currently used only in severe cases.

There are also non-piercing treatments. An example of them is the "cuckoo" method. Its other name is sinus washing according to Proets. The essence of this method is the circulation of liquid. The procedure is almost painless and does not require anesthesia. "Kukushka" is used in mild forms of goitre. At the beginning of the procedure, the patient is laid on his back, and one catheter is inserted into the nasal passages: the first one injects a special solution into the nasal cavity, and the second one takes it out. The course of treatment consists of approximately 7 treatments.

SURGICAL PRACTICE

Hymorotomy - in severe cases, it is used to sanitize the hyoid cavity and clean it from purulent mass, polyps, fungus and other infections. This practice is very effective, not complicated and does not leave unnecessary complications.

TREATMENT OF HYGIOMITIS USING FOLK MEDICINE

Statistics show that the percentage of effectiveness in the treatment of goitritis with the help of folk medicine is high. There are many recipes for drops, tinctures and ointments, and they are considered a cure for sinusitis. At the same time, they are not the main method of therapy and can be used only as a complex therapy. It is not recommended to use products that can cause allergies in the patient.

Remember!: If the disease is progressing and the symptoms are getting worse, don't delay visiting the doctor, folk medicine can be effective only in moderate and mild cases.

INHALATION

With propolis. Boil 2 liters of water in a pot. Add two teaspoons of alcohol solution of propolis to boiling water (available in pharmacies without a doctor's prescription). Bend over the bowl, cover your head with a towel and inhale the steam. If you have an allergic reaction to bee products, then it is not recommended to use this method.

With potatoes. In this method, one breathes in the vapors of freshly boiled potatoes. Duration is 15 minutes.

HONEY BASED DROP

Mix equal amounts of honey and aloe juice. Add a little water and drip 1-2 drops into the nose 2-3 times a day (bilaterally). Contraindications are as above.

RETAIL (OBLEPIXA) OIL

This vegetable oil is rich in healing properties and is used in the treatment of both acute and chronic sinusitis. 3-4 drops are instilled into the nose 3 times a day, then inhaling with the head down, the oil should not flow and go down the throat. Not recommended for children under 2 years of age.

COMPRESS USING LAUREL LEAVES

Pour boiling water over the bay leaves and wait a while. After cooling, soak a towel or any cloth in the prepared tincture and put it on the cheek area, keep the compress until it cools, repeat the procedure several times.

WARM

You can use this method if you are sure that there is no exudate (purulent or non-purulent) in the sinuses while the disease is being treated. Apply vaseline on the cheek area, then put a blue

lamp, if not, heated salt wrapped in a towel, apply the procedure 2-3 times a day. If there is an exudate in the sinus, it is not recommended to apply heat, because the exudate can expand and move to other areas.

This method should be used only during the recovery phase. It is necessary to get a doctor's recommendation before starting.

PREVENTION OF HYGIOMITIS

Prevention of any disease is better than cure. In order to prevent the disease, it is recommended to undergo a dental examination on time, not to walk a lot in cold weather, not to go outside without a hat in cold weather, and to treat colds and flu in time. Doing sports at least 10-20 minutes a day is useful for strengthening immunity.

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